

The philosophical system of 'Ubuntu' in Southern Africa

Secondary source

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The terms Ubuntu/Botho/Hunhu are of the local languages indigenous to southern Africa. They are of Zulu/Xhosa/Ndebele/Sesotho/Shona origin referring to the moral attribute of a person, who is known in the Bantu language as Munhu (Among the Shona of Zimbabwe), Umuntu (Among the Ndebele of Zimbabwe and the Zulu/Xhosa of South Africa) and Muthu (Among the Tswana of Botswana) and Omundu (Among the Herero of Namibia) to name just a few of the Bantu tribal groupings. Though the term has a wider linguistic rendering in almost all the Bantu languages of Southern Africa, it has gained a lot of philosophical attention in Zimbabwe and South Africa, especially in the early twenty-first century for the simple reason that both Zimbabwe and South Africa needed home-grown philosophies to move forward following political disturbances that had been caused by the liberation war and apartheid respectively.

Philosophically, the term Ubuntu emphasises the importance of a group or community and it finds its clear expression in the Nguni/Ndebele phrase: umuntu ngumuntu ngabantu which when translated to Shona means munhu munhu muvanhu (a person is a person through other persons). Hunhu/ubuntu is a traditional and/or indigenous philosophy focussing particularly on cohesion as distinctive features of groups, its components and how it is deployed in the public sphere.

Date Range: 1800 BCE - 2024 CE

Region: Southern Africa

Region tags: Middle Africa, Africa

Test

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Chitakure, J. 2020. Death Rituals Among the Karanga Of Nyajena, Zimbabwe: Praxis, Significance, and Changes. Pretoria: University Of South Africa
- Source 2: Kubvoruno, M. R. 2023. Zunde raMambo: A community innovation for food security and women's empowerment. Rozaria Trust.
- Source 3: Lan, D. M. 1983. Making history spirit mediums and the guerrilla war in the Dande area of Zimbabwe. London: Boston University.
- Source 1: Majeed, H. M. 2012. An examination of the concept of reincarnation in African philosophy.

- Source 2: Mandaza, D. M. 1974. Traditional ceremonies which persist. Gweru: Rhodesia Literature Bureau
- Source 3: Ministry of Education, Sport, Arts & Culture Ministry of Higher and Tertiary Education (MHTE)
- Source 1: MeDRA Programmes 2020 Annual Report
- Source 2: Politics Africa, 2021. Zimbabwe unveils statue of icon grandmother Nehanda. 25 May 2021.
- Source 3: Stathers, T., Sibanda, T., & Chigariro, J. 2000. The Zunde scheme, Chikomba district Zimbabwe. DFID.
- Source 1: The Reporter, Chief Njelele's formidable community court. The Sunday mail 5 April 2024
- Source 2: The reporter, 2024. President Mnangagwa hands over 100 vehicles to Chiefs. The Herald 29 February 2024.
- Source 3: International Religious Freedom Report for 2022 United States Department of State · Office of International Religious Freedom

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.marxists.org>Africa>
- Source 1 Description: Mbeki, G. 1964. South Africa: The peasant's revolt. London: South Africa National Liberation Movement. Mkwazhi, T. Pictures Alliance.
- Source 2 Description: Neil, S. 2009. Community court: official recognition and criminal jurisdiction, a comparative analysis. Pretoria: UNISA.
- Source 3 URL: <https://iep.utm.edu>hunhu-ubuntu...>
- Source 3 Description: Mangena, F. 2021. Hunhu/ Ubuntu in the traditional thought of Southrn Africa. An Encyclopedia of Philosophy articles written by Professional philosopher

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: not Applicable

Notes: Not applicable

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

- Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

- No

Notes: There is no competition since the cultural groups are for a specific clan that save their kinsmen

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: They are accommodating because of the ubuntu philosophy that encapsulates the hospitality concept. Late Archbishop Desmond Tutu made a statement which summarises the Ubuntu philosophy when he said; a person is a person through other persons. None of us comes into the world fully formed. We would not know how to think, or walk, or speak, or behave as human beings unless we learned it from other human beings. We need other human beings in order to be human. (Tutu, 2004:25).

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Ubuntu does not promote violence taping from its definition. The word Ubuntu is derived from a Nguni (isiZulu) aphorism: Umuntu Ngumuntu Ngabantu, which can be translated as “a person is a person because of or through others” (Moloketi, 2009:243; Tutu, 2004:2526). Ubuntu can be described as the capacity in an African culture to express compassion, reciprocity, dignity, humanity and mutuality in the interests of building and maintaining communities with justice and mutual caring (Khoza, 2006:6; Luhabe, 2002:103; Mandela, 2006:xxv; Tutu, 1999:3435).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The people form a defence force to protect their territories and boundaries against those who may come to invade or to colonise the community. These are joint efforts in defence of their sovereignty and territories from enemies.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: The system is natural because one is born in a community that is already religious from the African Traditional Religion. There is no need of conversion.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Members are born into the group. One does not need to grow up and make a choice to be an adherent of the African Traditional Religion as is done in Christianity. Ubuntu is a philosophical ideology of some indigenous southern African communities based on the principle of brotherhood, solidarity, unity and group cohesion. The people do not proselytise. They grow up within the confines of the ideology and take ownership of it to the overall advantage of the groups within which they live, thrive and find their relevance.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The spirit mediums as well as the political parties that seem to have liberative thrust are always associated with African Traditions.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: Custodians of African Tradition namely Chiefs, Kraal heads, herdsman, councillors and to some extent members of parliament are remunerated by government for their execution of duties. The Chiefs in particular are also given vehicles to move from one place to the other. Their homesteads were electrified this is in reference to Zimbabwe.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Yes

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: There is freedom of worship in Zimbabwe hence one is not punished because of apostacy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: 2% is said to be affiliated to ATR but there is syncretism in Southern Africa. Chitando asserts that every African is born into ATR.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 20

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Notes: see attached document

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:
– Number of levels [numeric value]: 4

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:
– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:
– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:
– No

↳ Powers are inherited:
– Yes

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:
– Yes

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):
– Yes

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:
– Yes

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
– Yes

- ↳ A political leader chooses the leader:
 - No
- ↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:
 - No
- ↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:
 - Yes
- ↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
 - Yes
- ↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:
 - Yes
- ↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
 - Yes

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: They rely on oral tradition

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 45

Notes: Most forests are regarded as sacred and they are reserved

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 30

Notes: Mbuya Nehanda statue in Harare

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 30

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 25

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 15

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 45

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Rivers and caves

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for some

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that

some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit does possess greater powers than human existence

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: It can possess any family member where it want to occupy (homwe in shona)

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: Underworld that is in the waters

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– No

Notes: It happens in spiritual form

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

Notes: Under normal circumstances it takes the form of animate objects

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– Yes

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the cultural beliefs

↳ Mummification:

– Yes

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Corpses are placed in graves for burial

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Notes: In normal cases they are laid to rest meaning they will be in a lying position. This can be for those who are placed in caves perhaps they are placed in standing position but the idea of making them rest is common in Africa.

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: Some may place the corpse in an animal skin depending on the cultural practices

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: This is done when one dies and buried in a foreign land and later on the parts are exhumed for reburial in one's mother land. It can also happen when one dies and buried in an area where it is not his or her original home area, some may take the soil at the grave site and have a second memorial site where the soil is buried as a symbol of honouring the deceased for failure to bring the corpse home.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Notes: This is not ideal in the cultural contexts of the deceased.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Sometimes it depends with the will of the deceased and the cultural practices

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: The mat, mahapa etc

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Burials in caves or memorial graves

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– Yes

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Notes: Supreme high god is a god of all people regardless of status

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: All knowing, ever present, loving

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: That which is beyond comprehension of humanity
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: This is normally when the god is angered by disobedience of humanity
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: They could be beyond recognition by human eyes but in spiritual forms

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: This could be a result of inviting the channel of communication through religious practices

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Revelation that may happen or kuratidzwa

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: They are only visible through manifestations

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Yes [specify]: Knowledge about death

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
– No

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: They are beyond recognition using human eyes since they will be in spiritual realm

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Yes

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- ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - Yes [specify]: Revelation
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - Notes: They are seen as ghosts or goritoto/dzimudzangara
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: They know about death

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Especially when they are angry

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Yes but they can not be comprehended by humanity

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:
 - Yes [specify]: Death cause

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: They may adapt to any environment around

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Yes [specify]: Revelation

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: Shrines are erected for veneration of gods

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: They care about environment

Notes: This is done through Indigenous knowledge systems

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Premarital sex

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Yes [specify]: Non living and environment

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Disobedience

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: To instill discipline

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the level of sin committed

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Punishment can be considered looking at the permission from the spiritual realm of ancestors. if they permit then you are punished. if they do not permit you are protected.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes
 - Notes: It can be through disasters experienced here and now

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No
- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes

Notes: Rewards are given as motivation and sign of acceptance

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes
 - Notes: Lucky in all adventures

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
 - No

- ↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:
 - No

- ↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other purpose:
 - Yes [specify]: Unifying people

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– Yes [specify]: Unknown time

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– Yes [specify]: Only those who are redeemed and selected

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– Yes

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– Only specialized religious class

– Only one class of society

– Only one gender

– All individuals within society (excepting slaves, aliens)

– All individuals within society

– All individuals within contemporary world

– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
– Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
– Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes

- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
– Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
– Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes

- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Yes [specify]: Transparency

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: It depends with the vows and type of spirit that possesses the person

- ↳ Monogamy (males):
 - Yes

- ↳ Monogamy (females):
 - Yes

- ↳ Other sexual constraints (males):
 - Yes

Notes: During fasting no sexual intercourse

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: When one is in her periods no sexual contact

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Church

Notes: Sacrifice will be in form of giving

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 4320

Notes: After a period of 6 months to a year

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 30

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 4320

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Normally done by the spirit

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: There is a concept of Zunde ramambo (Please note that Zunde raMambo is a traditional practice of bringing the community members together for a collective ploughing and planting at the Chief's place, the Kraal Head or the Village Head so that the Chief will in turn have enough harvest to provide to the needs of the vulnerable in the community).

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes through Zunde ramambo and food for work (Please see above for the meaning of the concept of Zunde raMambo).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: This is done through community leadership

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: Through Chiefs courts

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Patorialism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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